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D 9.1 Definition of Communication Strategy & Plan (Vers. I)

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Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail
Dalila Coviello	ERTICO	d.coviello@mail.ertico.com
Cordelia Wilson	ERTICO	c.wilson@mail.ertico.com
Daniele Brevi	LINKS Foundation	daniele.brevi@linksfoundation.com
Evi Brousta	ICCS	evi.brousta@iccs.gr
Elena Krikigianni	SEABILITY	e.krikigianni@seability.eu
Hatun Atasayar	AUSTRIATECH	hatun.Atasayar@austriatech.at

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Abstract
<p>This Communication Strategy and Plan provides a detailed and carefully designed overview of the communication activities that will be performed during the implementation of the ICT4CART project.</p> <p>The document describes broad communication and dissemination actions, aimed at reaching a wide range of target groups deploying the appropriate operational means.</p> <p>It will serve as the main reference for all communication activities and events over the course of the project, and outlines the strategies and measures to be employed by the ICT4CART project consortium in order to achieve its communication objectives. The presented set of processes will remain active throughout the lifetime of the project.</p>

Legal Disclaimer

The document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
D9.1	Deliverable number 1 of the Work Package number 9
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transportation System
M1	Month number 1 of the project course – (month in which a specific action takes place)
PO	Project officer
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

Context

Connected and automated vehicles are a key focal point of ITS research.

To enable and accelerate their deployment in our everyday life, ICT is a prerequisite; this is the frame in which ICT4CART project places itself.

Today, significant and rapid advances take place in the telecom and IT industries. Amongst these, ETSI ITS G5 has been thoroughly discussed at EU policy levels and has been used and tested in several EU projects. Moreover, 5G technology is evolving rapidly.

Despite the above, several ICT challenges related to connectivity, data management, cyber-security and ICT infrastructure architectures still exist, and need to be addressed in order to enable road vehicle automation. Advancing ICT infrastructure, with the exploitation of digital and ICT technologies, is essential.

ICT4CART aims to address the gaps to deployment bringing together key players from the automotive, telecom and IT industries, in order to shape the ICT landscape for Connected and Automated Road Transport and to boost EU competitiveness and innovation in this area.

Project scope

The main objective of ICT4CART is to design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure that will enable the transition towards higher levels of automation (up to L4), addressing existing gaps and working with specific key ICT elements, namely hybrid connectivity, data management, cyber-security, data privacy and accurate localisation.

ICT4CART builds on high-value use cases (urban and highway), which will be demonstrated and validated in real-life conditions at ICT4CART test sites in Austria, Germany and Italy. Significant effort will be put on cross-border interoperability, setting up a separate test site at the Italian-Austrian border.

D 9.1 Definition of Communication Strategy & Plan (Version I)

In this context, this document provides the initial communication strategy and plan, with a detailed overview of all communication and dissemination actions to be performed by the ICT4CART consortium. This initial communication strategy and plan includes the approach that will be used by ICT4CART partners to achieve an effective and efficient communication and dissemination of project news, outcomes and results; moreover, the document identifies the relevant objectives and target audience to address and the channel and means to be used, with the final aim of raising awareness

about ICT4CART’s scope.

Communication and dissemination activities involve all consortium partners and constitute an essential part of the project development and implementation. Related communication actions and dissemination activities have been assigned to each partner from the beginning of the project, in order to ensure ICT4CART high visibility, outreach and impact on all involved/interested actors.

1 Introduction

1.1 Definitions

Communication and dissemination are both essential in order to ensure the successful implementation of a project. Often, the difference between these two activities is not very clear, or some of the actions performed in their framework could be defined as both communication and dissemination.

The European Commission has recently provided with a thorough clarification and distinction between the two¹, as summarised in the following Table 1:

Communication	Dissemination
About the project and its results	About results only
Multiple audience Beyond the project’s own community (include the media and the public)	Audiences that may use the results in their own work e.g. peers (scientific or the project's own community), industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, policymakers
Inform and reach out to society , show the benefits of research	Enable use and uptake of results
Grant Agreement art. 38.1	Grant Agreement art. 29
Starts at the outset of the project	When results are available

Table 1: Communication and Dissemination differences

The main difference between communication and dissemination stands in their objectives, their focus and their targeted audience.

Communication aims at promoting the project, focusing on its results, challenges and achievements; it is a joint effort, in which the whole consortium is involved using all its available tools and means to effectively spread the project message to the widest public possible, including the media, using a set of standard communication practices which can be adapted to various settings and needs.

On the other hand, the primary goal of dissemination is to enhance the impact, visibility and credibility of the project, publicly sharing the results through the most effective and appropriate means (both

¹ A. Stasiak (June 2018), *H2020 Communication Dissemination & Outreach*, https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/6_sc2_coordinators_day_communication_and_dissemination.pdf

traditional media channels such as newsletters, publications, news media coverage and digital/social media). Peer reviewed scientific journals publications, scientific conferences presentation and industry related events participation fall under the dissemination actions.

1.2 Purpose of the document

Communication and dissemination of project activities are paramount actions to ensure effectiveness and sustainability of products and results, within and beyond the project lifetime.

A well-structured communication strategy is an effective instrument to maximise the impact of project results and outcomes, optimise their value and allow their active and concrete use in systems and practices at local, regional, national and European levels.

For these purposes, a consistent communication and dissemination strategy allows the consortium to identify, and subsequently measure, the extent to which project results reach the audience and are concretely utilised.

In ICT4CART, WP 9 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation” aims to ensure the broad dissemination of products and results throughout the entire project cycle and beyond.

As the first deliverable of WP 9, the Definition of Communication Strategy & Plan Version I (D 9.1) is designed to provide a structured framework of the communication and dissemination activities to be carried out during and after the ICT4CART project course. It has the main purpose of spreading project information and raising stakeholders and public’s awareness of the available products and results.

Specifically, the Plan defines both strategic approach and operational procedures adopted by the consortium to promote the project and disseminate its products and main results, with the purpose of defining a consistent and efficient method of disseminating progress in the project, through the planning of communication activities that will help to disseminate the ICT4CART project results as widely as possible.

The communication plan provides an exhaustive overview and sound categorisation of the various target groups and the activities to actively engage them in the project and to encourage their buy-in of the project results.

In addition, this document will describe communication procedures to be followed by all partners, as to efficiently promote ICT4CART and its results to the different target audiences.

The Communication Plan will be updated once a year (D9.2 and D9.3), based on an evaluation of the strategy’s effectiveness, making changes accordingly and prior communicated to the consortium.

The main communication tools will be also produced within this task (D9.4 and D9.5).

The ICT4CART Communication and Dissemination strategy will be based on five levels of

communication, as per the “5 Ws” Lasswell’s model² (who - Source, what - Message, in which channel or through which medium, to whom – the audience, and to what effect) and will be developed in accordance with the EC recommendations on Communication/Dissemination³.

It will ensure that there is a clear agreement amongst partners about the following key elements:

- Specific objectives for each of the target audiences;
- Channels/means to be used according to their special needs and nature;
- Activities to be performed in each development phase and the material to be released depending on the project progress;
- Specific plan and timeline to be followed for the performance of the respective activities;
- Key measures of their effectiveness of communication and dissemination effort and the roles of all participants in the communication flow and the procedures to be followed.

As ICT4CART developments concern not only a variety of scientific and technical communities, but also three different industries (automotive, telecom, IT), as well as non-technical audiences and general public, ICT4CART partners are highly committed to perform dedicated communication activities to convey the project messages and results to all related stakeholders’ communities.

The activities will be implemented using various channels and means, in order to raise attention and collect direct feedback.

In addition, the ICT4CART communication and dissemination activities will be planned and deployed in line with EU Policy and directives.

1.3 Intended readership

ICT4CART Communication Strategy and Plan intends to support all activities to promote the project’s results and to reach and engage the widest audience possible. It defines a range of activities and tools to communicate the project outcomes to relevant target groups.

This public deliverable is addressed to any interested reader, and, specifically, aims at providing ICT4CART’s consortium members with an extensive set of guidelines to plan and contribute the project’s promotion and diffusion.

² Lasswell, Harold (1948), *The Structure and Function of Communication in Society*, <https://pracownik.kul.pl/files/37108/public/Lasswell.pdf>.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/6_sc2_coordinators_day_communication_and_dissemination.pdf.

2 Communication strategy

2.1 Objectives

The main objectives of ICT4CART Communication Strategy and Plan are the following:

- To provide consortium partners with a set of useful guidelines to plan and perform communication and dissemination activities, with the final aim of maximising project's impact and reaching the wider audience possible;
- To ensure the production of high quality ICT4CART publications, presentations and other communication material;
- To avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- To establish a set of communication and dissemination best practices, in order to perform engaging and relevant dissemination and communication activities and to monitor and record them efficiently.
- To liaise with relevant projects, associations, networks and organisations to ensure the effective and efficient knowledge exchange.

2.2 Key audience

The identification of ICT4CART target audience is a vital part for the active engagement of stakeholders in the project communication and dissemination activities.

The consortium has already identified, at proposal stage, the targets it intends to approach, differentiating the communication and dissemination tools and activities to ensure participation and exploitation of the project results. Namely, ICT4CART key stakeholders are automotive manufacturers, telecom and IT industries, tier 1 suppliers, road operators and authorities, as shown in Table 2 below (together with the relevant impact of activities per target group):

Main results	Key message & timeline	Target	Communication activities	Relevant impact
Key results of ICT4CART as a EU-funded research project	Scientific, technological, societal achievements of the project (M01-M36)	Research community, policy makers, industrial players, general audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitive and widely recognisable brand identity; • Creation of a dedicated project website and social media accounts; • Project e-newsletter; • Performance of social media campaigns; • Specialised Press releases and other PR activities; • Bilateral discussions; • Communication kit; 	Evidence-based knowledge on ICT infrastructure architectures; Advancing public interest applications; Environmental and social benefits;

Main results	Key message & timeline	Target	Communication activities	Relevant impact
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Radio/television interviews; Scientific publications and technical presentations in renown Conferences and fairs; Final event and demonstration. 	Increased awareness at EU level and internationally
ICT4CART Architecture	How ICT4CART Architecture responds to the needs and interest of the targeted audience (M12-M36)	IT, Telecom, Automotive industries, road operators, service providers and other end user communities, innovative SMEs, standardisation bodies, relevant authorities and policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation/presentations/demonstrations to relevant events, such as conferences or fairs; Publications in specialised media and related conference proceedings; Articles in technical magazines and related industry technology publications; Participation at the ICT4CART Advisory Board and Stakeholder forum; Bilateral discussions and dedicated presentation in respective technical committees and fora; Social media activities and campaigns; ICT4CART Communication kit; Demo events at ICT4CART test sites (incl. cross-border); Final event and demonstration. 	Economic Impact; Environmental Impact; Evidence-based knowledge on ICT infrastructure architectures; Reliable data processing; Requirements for interoperability, latency, throughput, etc.; Open up of new market services; Feed into standardisation processes
ICT4CART hybrid communication component	How the adoption of such component will create market opportunities (M12-M36)			
Cyber-security and data privacy mechanisms	Contribution to the future work of large companies and SMEs in the area (M12-M36)			
Scientific results	Contribution of ICT4CART to the research community (M12-M36)	Researchers and scholars interested in the fields touched by ICT4CART	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conferences (IEEE ITSC, IEEE ITS, TRA, etc.) Peer-Reviewed publications in journals and magazines; Final Event and demonstration; ICT4CART website. 	Inform the research community, in EU and beyond, about ICT4CART developments
Basic notions and expected impact	How ICT4CART solutions will improve EU citizens everyday life (M01-M36)	Non-technical audiences and general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mass media (TV, radio) and social media activities; ICT4CART website; Communication kit; Final Event and demonstration; 	Economic impact; Social impact; Environmental impact

Table 2: Targeted audience

2.3 Key messages

ICT4CART key messages include the following:

- Raising awareness of the potential benefits of ICT4CART proposed technology;
- Engaging with target audiences to collect feedback for development;
- Dissemination of project results;
- Engaging with relevant R&D projects, associations/networks, standardisation bodies and organisations to ensure knowledge exchange, interoperability and wide market penetration;
- Engaging new and final users to contribute with inputs and feedbacks throughout the implementation of the project;
- Demonstrating how ICT4CART solutions are relevant for the daily life of European citizens.

Each key message will be specifically addressed to each of the selected target groups. Tailoring the messages, the consortium will ensure a significant impact of the diffused information and engage the audience according to their interests and needs, as further detailed in Table 2 of the previous section 2.2.

3 Tools and techniques

3.1 Communication channels

A variety of channels will be used, in order to effectively ensure ICT4CART information flow, create awareness and reach out to the targeted audiences by taking into account the specific characteristics and needs of each targeted group. The following indicative list of proposed communication channels shows the already selected tools to transmit project information, chosen by the consortium at proposal stage.

The list will be updated/modified as needed throughout the implementation of ICT4CART project and according to the project work plan, which foresees two updates of the Communication Strategy & Plan (D9.2 in M18 and D9.3 in M30):

- Project website;
- Press articles, online media (i.e. e-magazines) and press releases;
- Printed material;
- Social media channels;
- e-Newsletter;
- Short videos;

- Face-to-face meetings, conferences, seminars, workshops, events and others.

3.1.1 ICT4CART website

The project website has been designed with the purpose of making all kind of project information available and easily accessible for users. ICT4CART project website's domain is www.ict4cart.eu. Currently, the landing page of the website is available online. The full website will comprise, in addition to partners' description and project's objectives and vision, dedicated sub-sections with:

- detailed information about the four use cases;
- an information hub with public deliverables;
- presentations and media clips;
- news and event section;
- links to the project' social media accounts;
- official disclaimer as requested by the European Commission's guidelines;
- contact details of ICT4CART coordinator and ICT4CART dissemination manager.

ICT4CART website will also include the possibility to subscribe to the project mailing list to receive the latest updates through a newsflash, which will be issued every six months, starting from the end of Y1.

The website will be enriched and evolve throughout the implementation of the project, according to its outcomes, findings and results, to make sure to provide the users with accurate and up-to-date information.

Further details regarding ICT4CART's website will be included in D9.5 Communication Tools (V1), due in M6.

3.1.2 ICT4CART Social media

ICT4CART will be promoted through different social channels, which have been created to maximise the impact and give visibility to project events and news.

ICT4CART LinkedIn group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13642288/>) has been established as a community and facilitator for partners and stakeholders' discussions and idea exchanges. ERTICO is responsible of its maintenance and update with relevant information.

The consortium will promote ICT4CART LinkedIn group among its network and through each partner's social media, encouraging contacts to join and invite further participants, in order to maximising the

information diffusion and coverage.

The LinkedIn group counts, as of February 2019, 39 members (see Figure 1 below):

Figure 1: ICT4CART LinkedIn group

ICT4CART related content will also be promoted through Twitter, particularly to share “live” news related to project events and results. ICT4CART will benefit from two different Twitter accounts:

1. ERTICO Innovation ([@ERTICO](#)), with 6,248 followers as of February 2019 (see Figure 2 below);
2. ICT4CART dedicated Twitter account ([@ict4cart](#)), managed by SEABILITY in coordination with ICCS, counting 75 followers as of February 2019 (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 2: ERTICO Innovation Twitter account

Figure 3: ICT4CART Twitter account

All social media accounts comply with the guidelines provided in the EC Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects 2018⁴

3.1.3 ICT4CART Communication kit

ICT4CART will develop a communication kit to facilitate the information flow and promotion of the project to a wider audience, in particular when attending events, conferences and workshops.

ICT4CART communication kit includes:

- a flagship flyer to be produced in M6;
- a regular e-newsletter to be published every six months, starting from the end of the first year of the project, including the most relevant information, outcomes and results together with attended and upcoming events. ERTICO will coordinate this activity;
- short videos to be created from M18
- a set of ICT4CART roll-up banners;
- a project factsheet;
- ICT4CART giveaways with QR code linking to the project website;
- one professional video.

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

3.1.4 ICT4CART Brand identity

The consortium has developed a consistent and coherent brand identity for ICT4CART, as part of the D9.4 “Brand Identity & Guidelines”, submitted in M3.

This set of recommendations includes a thorough description of the main brand elements (logo, brand, fonts and colours, social media banners, project tagline, PowerPoint presentations and Word documents templates) to ensure quality, consistency and style to each project outcome (see Annex 1).

All ICT4CART dissemination and communication products will follow the aforementioned procedures, in order to achieve uniformity and a distinct identity and recognition.

Moreover, the guidelines include a section dedicated to the appropriate use of EU logo and disclaimer, in order to guarantee the compliance of all ICT4CART material with the European recommendations for EU-funded Research and Innovation projects.

3.1.5 Press articles, online media and press releases, technical and scientific publications

ICT4CART consortium partners will utilise all opportunities to systematically disseminate project’s results through the media.

A press release has been already issued at the beginning of the project, after the kick off meeting which was held in Athens in September 2018. The press release was circulated among the consortium and shared by each partner through its website and social media channels. The press release, fully available in Annex 2 of this deliverable, raised the attention of the local press in some of the areas interested by ICT4CART activities and implementation. Particularly, some German regional newspapers wrote about ICT4CART’s launch (all articles are in German):

- the Augsburger Allgemeine Zeitung, a major German regional daily newspaper: <https://www.augsburger-allgemeine.de/neu-ulm/Zukunft-des-Fahrens-beginnt-in-Ulm-id52915926.html>, reach: 962k;
- the Schwabische Zeitung, one of the largest regional subscription newspapers in Baden-Württemberg: https://www.schwaebische.de/landkreis/alb-donau-kreis/ulm_artikel,-ulm-wird-testfeld-f%C3%BCr-automatisiertes-fahren-arid_10978204.html, reach: 326k;
- the Sudweste Presse, a German daily newspaper based in Ulm: <https://www.swp.de/suedwesten/staedte/ulm/automatisiertes-fahren-ulm-erhaelt-zuschlag-28655620.html>, reach: 2.18k;
- Autonomes Fahren & co., a German magazine for Autonomous Cars, Autonomous Systems,

Assistance Systems and Telemetry: <https://www.autonomes-fahren.de/ulm-weitet-sein-testfeld-aus/>, reach: 2.94k⁵.

Following the first press release disseminated at the start of the project, regular press releases will continue to be produced and circulated among the consortium with ICT4CART news, events and results. This will assist the consortium in sharing project news to their media contacts. Such content will be promoted through the official ICT4CART website and social media, but also via consortium members' corporate and private accounts, to ensure maximum impact.

The consortium will also take advantage of EC publication means, such as the Horizon Magazine, Futuris Magazine etc. to publish project news and achievements.

For a detailed plan of the publication activities, see section 3 below.

3.1.6 Meetings, conferences and events

The participation and organisation of meetings, conferences and events is one of the most effective strategies to reach directly the targeted audience.

ICT4CART planned events organisations include:

- 4 dedicated ICT4CART special sessions;
- 3 demonstration events in each pilot site;
- ICT4CART International Conference with final system demonstration and press conference.

Furthermore, ICT4CART consortium members will maximise their participation to events, conferences and workshop to ensure proactive networking and dissemination of project's results and outcomes.

A detailed plan of the events organisation activities is included in the following section 3.2.

3.2 Dissemination Activities and Event Organisation

3.2.1 Dissemination and event activities plan and coordination

In the context of ICT4CART, special attention is given to the project's dissemination activities as well as in the event organisation and participation, throughout the course of the project. By effectively exploiting such opportunities, ICT4CART aims to achieve wide acceptance and scale up of the project advances and results by a critical mass of interested stakeholders and communities in the automotive industry. These opportunities are referred, but not limited, to the following:

- The participation in European and international conferences, specialized meetings, fora,

⁵ Reach data as of January 2019. Source: www.meltwater.com

working groups.

- The organization of dedicated events (e.g. Special Interested Sessions, demonstration events, International conference etc.)
- The publication in peer review scientific & technical journals, conference proceedings and high reputational magazines, particularly targeting the open access resources.

ICT4CART attempts to directly reach the relevant target audiences and to endow the ICT4CART project with higher visibility and impact. The effective engagement of the project will be ensured through technical papers and articles, oral and/or poster presentations, booths and visits to international conferences, press conferences and audio-visuals.

SEAB, as T.9.2 Leader, has proceeded, since the project kick-off, with the creation of a repository for ICT4CART events and journals that are considered as valuable opportunities for the project. The repository includes an indicative list of proposed scientific journals and an indicative list of proposed upcoming European and international events (Annex 3) and it is regularly updated mainly by T.9.2 Leader and by the consortium partners. In addition, ICT4CART partners are regularly informed through emails about upcoming key opportunities so they will be able to benefit from them.

Moreover, in order for ICT4CART to produce high quality publications and presentations and to avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information, ICCS, as project coordinator, has provided the consortium with a set of dissemination procedures. The procedures include guidelines and set out the main steps to be followed by partners for the publication or presentation of the work done within the framework of the ICT4CART project. The full description of the communication/dissemination procedures for ICT4CART is available through the common online collaborative tool (Redmine) and also in sub-section 4.2 of the present document.

The finalisation of every dissemination and/or communication activity within ICT4CART project is registered and described in the Dissemination activities report template, in order to facilitate the constant monitoring and tracking of ICT4CART activities. More information about the template and its use are provided in sub-section 4.2 of the current document.

3.2.2 Performed activities

The activities that have been performed during the first six months (M1-M6) of ICT4CART implementation are listed in Table 3 below:

Conferences

- ITS World 2018, SIS36: ICT Serving Automated Road Transport, Copenhagen, 18/09/2018, ICCS, ERTICO, IBM-Z, NOKIA,
- Project présentation at the EUCAD 2018 Conference in Vienna, on 20 April 2018 ICCS
Publications
- TRA2018, End-to-End latency in HAD applications using cloud technology, Copenhagen, 18/04/2018,Vienna, Austria, "doi: 10.5281/zenodo.1486544",ASFINAG
Other activities
- ICT4CART project Overview, Presentation to Ricardo corp company, 22/11/2018, AIRBUS
Mass Media Publications
- Press meeting at the Ulm townhall, 11/12/2018, Ulm University, Nokia, BMW and Swarco
Project events
- Kick-off meeting, Athens-Greece, 11-12/09/2018, All partners - 2 nd Plenary meeting, Vienna, Austria, 28-29/11/2018

Table 3: ICT4CART performed communication activities M1-M6

3.3 Communication for use cases

ICT4CART consortium will dedicate particular attention to the use cases scheduled during the project implementation.

ICT4CART builds on four specific high-value use cases (urban and highway), which will be demonstrated and validated under real-life conditions at the following test sites:

- Austria;
- Germany;
- Italy;
- Italian- Austria border.

All the above-mentioned have been selected based on specific criteria, such as their alignment with EU policy and relevant fora and initiatives, their significant impact on connected automation, their potential to generalise on the results, and, finally, their level of interest for the consortium members and relevance to their industrial roadmaps.

The consortium has foreseen a specific “sub-strategy” for communication and dissemination to be put in place around the four events, in order to make the most out of them in terms of engagement and exposure.

As shown in Table 4 below, each action will be implemented to achieve a specific result and partners will utilise all available tools to convey the message and target a wider audience.

Activity	Description	Objective
Social media activities	Twitter and LinkedIn will be used to share in advance, during and after each use case event the main news and achievements.	Share relevant and engaging content on the goals reached through the use cases events. Enlarge the audience sharing on partners' private network and using relevant hashtags.
Articles and press releases	A constant flow of press releases related to each event will be circulated and posted on ICT4CART website and social channels	Keep the project website and channels constantly updated with news and results from the use cases events.
Local press	The consortium will engage the local press, local radio/news channels and local authorities to actively participate and disseminate the use cases.	Involve citizens and mobilise stakeholders at local level to maximise the events' impact.
Video clips	Videos and shorter video clips will be taken during the event; the footage will be shared as relevant project content.	Create a video information hub on project website and channel to provide engaging content, easy to share and able to reach more final users.
Interviews	ICT4CART consortium will use the test sites events as an occasion to organise interviews among partners and external experts/stakeholders, to gather relevant insights and enrich the online project content.	Provide a different point of view and elaborate on core topics of the project.
Citizens involvement	Use cases events will be used as an occasion to engage citizens in the different test sites and encourage them to actively participate to the demonstrations.	Raise awareness at local level and extend the number of involved audience creating online traffic on ICT4CART channels.

Table 4 – Communication for use cases

4 Communication and dissemination procedures

4.1 Partners' role and efforts

ERTICO, WP Leader for WP9 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation”, is responsible for the definition of the communication and dissemination strategy of ICT4CART and its updates, together with the development of the communication tools. Moreover, it will be involved in the organisation of ICT4CART events.

ERTICO will be in continuous contact with all project partners, equally supporting on tasks under its responsibility and engaged on other tasks under WP9. The smooth and constant internal communication will ensure to meet deadlines and objectives, in close cooperation with the project coordinator, ICCS.

Detailed roles and responsibilities under WP9, as well as the allocated effort per partner, are described in Tables 5 and 6 below:

Partner	Role and responsibilities
ERTICO	WP leader for WP9 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation; Task 9.1 leader, responsible for the definition of the communication and dissemination strategy and the development of communication tools; involved in the organisation of ICT4CART events
ICCS	ICCS participates at the Task 9.1 activities, is responsible for the organisation of the Final Event in cooperation with Seability and contributes to the liaison and standardisation effort of the project (Task 9.3, Task 9.6)
NOKIA	Leader of the exploitation strategy (Task 9.4)
SEAB	Leader of T9.2; responsible of planning and coordinating partners' efforts to properly disseminate project findings; assisting test site leaders in the organisation of the events; organising the final event with ICCS.
CRF	Responsible for the organisation of the ICT4CART event in the Italian test site, along with SEAB
UULM	Responsible for the organisation of the ICT4CART event in the German test site, along with SEAB.
ASFINAG	Responsible for the organisation of the ICT4CART event in Austria, along with SEAB
ALL	Participate in the ICT4CART dissemination activities (T9.2)

Table 5 – Partners' role

Partner	WP9 effort
ICCS	12.00
IBM-IE	3.00
IBM-Z	1.00
CRF	2.00
BMW	1.00
NOKIA	7.00
WIND	1.50
T-MOB	7.00
BOSCH	1.00
SWM	5.00
AIRBUS	2.00
ASFINAG	7.00
ATE	7.00
UULM	2.00
SEAB	14.00
ISMB	4.00
ERTICO	13.00
COU	1.50
CDV	1.50
BRE	1.50
UFL	10.00
Total	104.00

Table 6 – WP9 effort per partner

4.2 Detailed Dissemination procedures and activity report

4.2.1 Detailed Dissemination procedure

SEABility, in quality of Task 9.2 “Dissemination activities and Events organisation” leader, has provided the consortium with detailed Dissemination procedures to be followed during the implementation of the different activities, with the basic objective of producing high-quality communication materials, avoiding overlaps and disclosure of confidential information.

The participation of any Partner in an event, as well as the performance of every dissemination activity related to ICT4CART project, has to be approved beforehand by the ICT4CART Project Coordinator and the project Steering Committee (SC).

To this purpose, a template to submit a dissemination activity request has been set up by SEABility (“Dissemination Requests Table”).

Any dissemination activity request needs to be submitted, through the above-mentioned template, at least two weeks in advance, via email, to the WP9 leader (ERTICO) and the Task 9.2 Leader (SEABILITY). The material related to the proposed activity (abstract, draft paper, poster, article, presentation, press release etc.) needs to be prior stored in the related folder which has been created on the common project working space (Redmine).

Task 9.2 Leader has 2 days to react and send the request to Coordinator/Steering Committee for approval, modification or rejection. Coordinator/ Steering Committee, on their side, have 5 working days to send their decision to the Task 9.2 Leader; no answer received within this deadline will be considered as an approval.

Task 9.2 Leader will then inform the involved partner(s) about the decision.

In case of approval, partner(s) can proceed to implement the proposed activity; in case of conflict or objection, due to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information, Steering Committee members can reject the proposed activity or ask for modifications, additions or further material. The new material is proposed again to WP9 and Task 9.2 Leaders and if significant changes must be made, the previous procedure is followed.

4.2.2 Dissemination activities report

In addition, to ensure constant monitoring and tracking of the dissemination and communication activities carried out by ICT4CART consortium, a Dissemination activities report has been set up, to be filled in within ten working days after the realisation of the approved dissemination activity, accompanied by the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.).

The detailed Dissemination procedures, together with the Dissemination activities requests table and the Dissemination activities report, are available on Redmine.

5 Key Performance Indicator

Measurable targets for dissemination activities have been set in order to ensure that the desired impact is achieved. Table 6 below describes the planned ICT4CART Communication and Dissemination activities to be performed in the different project phases and KPIs expected from each of them:

Activity	Description	KPI	Expected result
Brand identity	A coherent and consistent brand identity has been created to ensure ICT4CART visual products to be effective and recognisable, explaining the project meaning and core idea in a clear way.	Logo, procedures and guidelines, Word template, PPT template, visuals that are connected with the brand that is used on the website and flyer	Immediate recognition by stakeholders on all information material and at events when consortium presents project information.
Project website	Launch, maintenance and update of ICT4CART website as a hub of relevant information, news and events related to the project.	Public website with specific sections for the different topics and products.	100 unique visitors per month
Communication kit	A communication kit will be produced to facilitate the information flow and promotion of the project.	Flagship flyer, ICT4CART newsletter (every 6 months); short videos (starting from M18), roll-up banners, 1 professional video.	A wider understanding of the objectives and aims of the project by stakeholders.
Social media channels	Social media will be used to spread project-related news, raising awareness about the core topics and achievements, promote ICT4CART events and disseminate public results (deliverables, articles etc.)	LinkedIn project group; ICT4CART tweets (using established ERTICO Innovation Twitter account). Project channels will be regularly updated (weekly base); partners will contribute sharing the content on their own corporate accounts.	Throughout the project, At least 500 followers for Twitter; at least 150 members for LinkedIn; at least 10 posts shared per partner in individual social accounts; at least 70 announcements in social media channels; at least 2 social media campaigns.
Conferences/events	ICT4CART consortium will be presented in relevant conferences and other events. Partners' effort will focus on sharing consortium organised events and attending external sessions to disseminate project content, engaging targeted audience.	List of relevant events with a minimum level of participation guaranteed; minimum number of attendees/participants engaged.	At least 10-15 events attended/year; at least 20 conference publications; at least 47 conference presentations; at least;
Technical papers & journal articles	ICT4CART technical papers will be published in conference proceedings while research articles will be submitted to peer-reviewed scientific and technology journals.	Technical papers and research articles.	At least 3 papers/year; at least 4 journal articles in total.
Use of EU dissemination networks & tools	ICT4CART consortium will seek every opportunity to utilise the means offered by the EU such as	Publications in EU tools and participation to EU events.	At least 5 publications and at least 5 events attended throughout the implementation of the project.

Activity	Description	KPI	Expected result
	H2020 magazine & others, to promote project's results.		
Project events	ICT4CART includes in its implementation 3 pilot sites demonstration events and one final International conference to achieve wider communication of activities.	Pilot-site demonstration events; final project event.	3 pilot-site events; & final international conference; at least 50 attendees per event for demonstration events; at least 120 participants for final international conference.
e-Newsletter	ICT4CART will produce and circulate a project newsletter starting from the end of year 1 to update the audience about project results and events.	4 e-Newsletter issues circulated to a list of subscribers	At least 230 estimated recipients of the project e-newsletter
Media coverage	Press releases will be issued frequently to achieve the publication of articles in popular and/or specialized media. ICT4CART partners will use every available local, national and European press contact they have, in order to communicate the overall project advances and results.	Press releases circulated to external press and online media to promote ICT4CART to a wide range of professionals and the general public.	25 estimated pieces of media clips achieved throughout project's implementation.
Liaison & networking activities	ICT4CART will involve different groups in its activities in order to communicate the basic principles and the implementation of the relevant ICT tools proposed	Liaison with related EU and international R&D initiatives, policy makers and related organizations; creation of synergies with past and future R&D projects and; liaison with already established networks, associations, organizations, related fora and technical communities.	At least 10 EU & national projects networked; at least 20 liaison activities performed; at least 8 organisations/platforms/associations networked;
Standardisation activities	In the design and development phase, ICT4CART will contribute to European standardisation thanks to the strong connection with the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)	Provide a strategic study on the existing and under development standards relevant for the ICT4CART project; liaise with relevant standardisation groups.	At least 5 standardisation bodies and TCs networked
Workshops/special sessions/discussions	ICT4CART will include workshops, discussions and special sessions in the variety of channels used to ensure information flow and reach out to the targeted audiences.	Transmit project information, raise awareness, increase the project's impact size, extend the network.	At least 4 special sessions/workshops organised; at least 12 discussions in fora, committees and organisations
Advisory board & Stakeholder forum	In the context of the liaison activities, ICT4CART will institute an Advisory board and a Stakeholder forum to ensure better diffusion of project's information and monitor dissemination & communication activities.	Promotion of the project's approach for the adoption of automated driving; synchronise efforts, explored synergies and avoid double work.	At least 20 Advisory board members; at least 230 Stakeholder Forum members

Table 7 – Communication & Dissemination activities KPIs

6 Liaison and Networking Activities

In order to communicate the ICT4CART basic principles and the implementation of the relevant ICT tools proposed by ICT4CART, the partners will involve different groups in their activities. Within the framework of Task 9.3, the planning and execution of ICT4CART liaison with related EU and international R&D initiatives, policy makers and related organizations will be realised. The main outcome of liaison and networking activities will be to widely promote the project's holistic approach for the adoption of automated driving, synchronised efforts, explored synergies and avoidance of double work. To achieve this, the focus of Task 9.3 will be

- a) Establishment of the Advisory Board and Stakeholder Forum,
- b) Creation of synergies with past and future R&D projects and
- c) Liaison with already established networks, associations, organizations, related fora and technical communities.

6.1 Networking and knowledge exchange

To maximise its impact, increase synergies and avoid overlaps ICT4CART will build on existing initiatives and projects in the EU in the field of connected and automated road transport. The Consortium has already established strong links with all major activities, mainly through common partners. Regional, national and European authorities will also be contacted and informed about the benefits of the ICT4CART ICT infrastructure for the promotion of Highly Automated Driving in Road Transport. Figure 4 and Table 8 below provide details in relation to the groups of stakeholders and their engagement plan throughout ICT4CART's implementation:

Figure 4 – Overview of relevant Stakeholder

Stakeholder engagement plan	Start	End
Identifying stakeholders	M01	M06
Formation of groups and election of representatives for the Advisory Board	M05	M18
Focused engagement with key stakeholders on specific aspects, communication through established channels (meetings, demonstration events)	M13	M36
Communication with the Stakeholder Forum through e-newsletters, social media campaigns, etc.	M13	M36
Up-to-date information provided through the project's website about the consortium's work progress and outcomes to end-users and general public	M07	M36
A number of periodic social media campaigns/activities to inform and attract frequent social media users and invite them to provide feedback. This channel will be used to expand the members of the ICT4CART Stakeholders Forum.	M01	M36
Special press releases and other PR activities will be sent to various media outlets across Europe to promote to a wide range of professionals and the general public.	M01	M36
Scientific publications and technical presentations in renown conferences and fairs	M01	M36
Participation/presentation/demonstrations in relevant events	M01	M36
Bilateral discussions and dedicated presentations in respective technical committees and fora	M01	M36
Creation of synergies with past and future R&D and implementation projects	M01	M36
Liaison activities with networks, associations, organizations, related fora and technical communities	M03	M36

Table 8 – Stakeholder engagement plan

6.2 Advisory Board and Stakeholder Forum

To ensure an effective networking and knowledge exchange, an Advisory Board will be formed in M6 by external professionals, involving different groups (automotive, ICT, telecommunication, academia) and utilising the networks existing in the consortium.

ICT4CART partners working in the automotive sector will contact related organisations and associations within their network to inform them about the project's vision and objectives and consult on the ICT4CART use cases and proposed ICT Infrastructure. The partners working in the field of telecommunication will include professionals from the related industry to provide their feedback regarding the proposed hybrid communication approach, network slicing and edge computing in the interoperable IT environment. Academic partners will involve professional researchers from their institutions as well as professors/researchers in the area of Transport, Telecommunications and Automation, inviting them to give feedback about the proposed infrastructure. The members of the Advisory Board are more likely to be experts from platforms, organizations and associations rather

than from specific companies. The number of Board members will intentionally be limited, in order to ensure a manageable size.

This Advisory Board is the core of a broader group of experts and relevant stakeholders that forms the ICT4CART Stakeholder Forum. The Advisory Board, as well as the Stakeholder Forum, will be represented equally in quality through experts from each area (automotive, ICT, telecommunication, academia), to ensure that all relevant stakeholder groups are represented. The Stakeholder Forum will continuously extend during project’s duration and will be kept informed on a regular basis about ICT4CART major achievements and work progress through the ICT4CART e-newsletter, the social media activities, press articles, physical meetings etc.

Moreover, the Stakeholder Forum members will be invited to the ICT4CART demonstration events to learn more about the proposed solutions and provide feedback according to their needs.

During the project, demonstration events will be held at each ICT4CART test site (Italy, Austria and Germany), in order to showcase the ICT4CART solutions to the members of the Advisory board and the Stakeholder Forum, as well as to relevant authorities and standardisation bodies, end user communities, related industries, researchers, academia and any other interested persons. The integration and testing activities at the different test sites will be defined in WP 7.

In addition, an international Conference will be held at the end of the project to present ICT4CART’s results through technical and live demonstrations to a large number of stakeholders. The full list of stakeholders and members of the Advisory Board is provided in Table 9 and 10 below.

Stakeholder groups	Stakeholder	Stakeholder Forum
Organisations and associations in the field of automotive or ICT	ACEA	YES
	Amsterdam Group	YES
	AUVSI	YES
	California PATH	YES
	ERTRAC	YES
	EUCAR	YES
	TRB	YES
	NDS Association	YES
	EARPA	YES
	CLEPA	YES
	Car-2-Car Communication Consortium	YES
	5GAA	YES
	EATA	YES
	ERTRAC WG on Connectivity and Automated Driving	YES
Related platforms and fora	Open AutoDrive Forum	YES

Stakeholder groups	Stakeholder	Stakeholder Forum
	iMobility Forum	YES
	SENSORIS Innovation Platform.	YES
	EU EIP - Sub-activity 4.2	YES
	European Automotive Telecom Alliance	YES
R&D or implementation projects	CARTRE/ARCADE	YES
	C-Roads	YES
	CONCORDA	YES
	L3Pilot	YES
	NeMo	YES
	SAFERtec	YES
	SerIoT	YES
	CTI (Cybersecurity for Intelligent Transport)	YES
	INFRAMIX	YES
	AUTOPILOT	YES
	InterCor	YES
	ABC4Trust	YES
	5G-MOBIX	YES
	interACT	YES
	HEADSTART	YES
	BRAVE	YES
	RobustSENSE	YES
	MAVEN	YES
	5G-CARMEN	YES
	SecForCARS (DE)	YES
MEC-View (DE)	YES	
Socrates	YES	
BASt	YES	
Infrastructure and road authorities (regional, national and European) Organizations (public or private) responsible for the correct management of road infrastructure	Attikes Diadromes SA	YES
	Hellastron	YES
	ASECAP	YES
	A22 - Autobrennero	YES
	Autostrade per Italia	YES
	Cofiroute	YES
	Sanofi	YES
	Abertis	YES
	OHLconcessionaires	YES
	ASFINAG	YES
	ERA chair ITS	YES
	FEHRL	YES
	NTUA/ICCS	YES
	DLR	YES
	Fraunhofer	YES
	TUM	YES
	University Eindhoven	YES
POLIMI	YES	

Stakeholder groups	Stakeholder	Stakeholder Forum
	e-mobil BW	YES
	European Commission	YES
Public authorities, policy makers Decision makers, city planners and other public authorities at different geographical levels	POLIS Network	YES
	Greek Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport	YES
	Greek Ministry of Telecommunications and Networks	YES
	ERTRAC	YES
	BMVIT	YES
	RWS (NL)	YES
	BMVI (GER)	YES
	DG Move	YES
	DG Connect	YES
	RTD	YES
	ETSI	YES
	3GPPP	YES
	OneM2M	YES
	IEC	YES
	Standardisation bodies and technical committees	CEN
ISO - WG3 extended Vehicles		YES
SAE		YES
UNECE World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations		YES

Table 9: ICT4CART Stakeholder Forum

ID	Organization/project	Area of expertise					profession					
		ICT Architecture	Hybrid connectivity	Data Management and Services	Cyber-security/ Data privacy	Accurate localisation	Researcher/ academic	Road operators	Telecom operators	ICT/Equipment provider	OEMs/Automotive industry	others
1	ERA chair ITS (http://www.erachair.uniza.sk/team2/era-chair/)	X		X	X		X					
2	AUVSI	X					X			X	X	X
3	C2C Communication Consortium	X	X								X	X
4	AVL	X	X	X			X				X	
5	BasT		X					X				
6	ASECAP			X				X				
7	SecForCARS				X			X				
8	Oppida				X							X
9	Technical university of Munich		X				X					
10	DLR					X	X					
11	Hellastron			X				X				
12	European Automobile Manufacturers' Association (ACEA)			X							X	
13	CLEPA		X	X							X	
14	ETNO https://etno.eu/home/about-us/etno-office	X							X			
15	ECTA, https://www.ectaportal.com/	X							X			
16	ETSI	X	X	X					X			
17	Navigation Data Standard (NDS) e.V. Association					X						X
18	Hungarian Road Operator Magyar Kozut			X		X		X				

Table 10: The table presents the potential Members of the Advisory Board

6.3 Liaison Activities

Networking with relevant associations, organisations and European R&D initiatives is very important since this will ensure knowledge interchange between key actors and the adoption of proposed solutions. First collaborations have already taken place within the framework of joint preparations of various presentations for example for conferences and other events (table 11).

No.	Name of organisation	Status of collaboration	On regard to task force/topic
1	INFRAMIX	established	Hybrid infrastructure,
2	C-Roads	established	C-ITS
3	CONCORDA	established	Connected services and technologies
4	C2C CC	in discussion	C-ITS
5	5G-MOBIX	in discussion	Similar scope as ICT4CART
6	5G-PPP/5GIA	planned	5G project x-Coordination
7	5GAA	planned	5G and automotive
8	ETSI Multi Access EDGE Computing (MEC) group	planned	MEC applications in ICT4Cart ISMB is a group member and can present the ICT4CART activities in the group
9	ETSI Collective Perception Messages Working group	planned	use of CPM messages in a real UC
10	WG for intelligent mobility – Electricmobility South-West Germany	established	Intelligent mobility

Table 11: Status liaison activities

7 Standardisation Activities

Standardisation is one of the main objectives of the ICT4CART project, as stated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement.

In the design and development phase, ICT4CART will not only use standard approaches but will also contribute to European standardisation thanks to the strong connection with the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) contributing with a signed Letter of Support for ICT4CART.

The task 9.6 will start at month 13, end at month 36 and it will be led by LINKS Foundation (formerly ISMB) with the participation of ICCS, BMW, NOKIA, T-MOB, ASFINAG, ATE.

The plan of this task can be summarised in the following two main objectives:

1. Provide a strategic study on the existing and under development standards relevant for the ICT4CART project. This analysis will be included in the Deliverable 9.7 Final report on communication,

dissemination and liaison due at M36. It will help in identifying possible standardization areas where ICT4CART Partners may contribute;

2. Liaise with relevant standardisation groups and ensure that ICT4CART is building upon emerging standards toward facilitating the acceptance and utilisation by the market of the developed solutions within the ICT4CART project.

In month 13, the requirements (WP2) and the architecture definition (WP3) phases of the project will be closed. The results coming from these WPs will be the basis to better understand possible areas of contribution. Indeed, at that stage it would be clear which technical solutions should be implemented and which of them can provide input to standardization activities.

The already selected standardization topics to be investigated are:

- Frequency spectrum issues for cellular (e.g. 700MHz) and ad-hoc networks (e.g. 5.9GHz)
- Multi Access Edge Computing (MEC)

A kick-off conference call will be organised at M13 and periodic calls will be planned to discuss the progress of the various actions and to understand if further standardization activities can be undertaken depending on the outcomes of the technical work carried out within the ICT4CART project. Dedicated slots for discussion will be established when necessary during physical meetings.

For each standardisation activity, a partner will be appointed as responsible for conducting the work. The partner will take all the required actions to successfully accomplish the standardisation activity. The responsible partner will involve other relevant partners and it will coordinate standardization work among them.

8 Risk Management

A dedicated risk management section will be provided in D1.1 Quality and Risk Management Plan. Table 12 below, though, has the purpose of clarifying the mitigation strategies the consortium has put in place to face communication-related risk elements, as the communication and dissemination activities are considered vital for a successful implementation of the project.

ICT4CART partners expect to tackle those issues a priori, relying on a smooth and constant internal communication and the large experience in project management of each partner.

The consortium will tackle any unexpected event through cooperation and strategic thinking.

Risk	Mitigation measures	Probability	Potential Damage
Low involvement of external audience	The communication kit and tools have been created at early stage to be tailored on targeted audience; the consortium relies on an already established network of stakeholders to support the project and disseminate its results.	Medium	Medium
Low outreach of ICT4CART communication channels	Communication channels will be regularly updated with relevant content to reach targeted audience and involve users; moreover, communication strategy and plan will be constantly monitored and adapted as needed, to ensure the reach of expected KPIs. Channels' insights will be periodically reviewed to guarantee a constant growth of engaged audience.	Low	High
Low participation in project's events	Project's events will be duly promoted in advance to broaden the number of participants in ICT4CART's activities. Partners will put particular effort to reach their network through their private channels and ensure engagement.	Low	High

Table 12 – Communication activities risks – mitigation measures

9 Conclusions

This deliverable presented the Initial ICT4CART Communications Strategy and Plan, which will be used as a guide for the consortium members to ensure a correct and effective implementation of communication and dissemination activities and maximise the project's impact.

This deliverable described ICT4CART's approach to communication and defined its key concepts, targeted audiences, main content and engagement plan together with the foreseen online and offline communication and dissemination activities. Furthermore, it included the detailed Dissemination procedures and brand identity guidelines for ICT4CART's partners to follow.

The Initial ICT4CART Communications Strategy and Plan is considered a living document; it will be further updated in M18 and M30, as per the project's work plan, adapting ICT4CART communication's tools and means as needed to ensure that project's results and information are effectively communicated throughout its implementation and beyond.

Annexes

Annex 1 – Brand identity & guidelines

1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to properly present the ICT4CART project brand identity already developed since the beginning of the project, in order to serve as the basis of all communication and impact creation activities of the ICT4CART project. A set of specific guidelines are also provided to assist the consortium in using correctly the project logo and produced MS office templates and material. The guidelines are considered also as a useful aid when instructing typographers and others employed to produce branded items and to design and create ICT4CART communications material. In order to maintain the integrity of the ICT4CART project brand identity, it is important that all given instructions are applied properly.

The project communications material and all the brand elements can be used freely by all consortium members, however all external bodies, except for the European Commission, must acquire the required permission from the consortium, before proceeding with any use of the ICT4CART material.

1.1.1 Brand, logo and fonts

1.1.1.1 ICT4CART Brand identity

ICT4CART brand is the first thing people see when encountering the project. The brand represents the project, its personality and appearance. It is important to ensure that the ICT4CART brand integrity is always maintained.

The golden rule when using the core elements of the ICT4CART brand identity is to use them consistently and in-line with the guidelines and the communication procedures (available in the common online collaborative tool (Redmine)) as presented in the current document. In any other case, possible occurred inconsistencies may lead to confusion and weaken the project's branding. The correct application of these guidelines, ensures that ICT4CART messages are always clear, they reinforce each other and they always express the true character of the ICT4CART brand.

1.1.1.2 ICT4CART Logo: the concept

The starting point for a project brand story is based around the core activities of the project shortly presented through its full title: "ICT Infrastructure for Connected and Automated Road Transport".

Being the recognisable element of the project visual identity, the ICT4CART logo visually depicts the basic aspects of ICT4CART's core activities.

For best serving the impact creation activities of the project a bold, versatile logo has been created. ICT4CART logo (Figure 1), consists of two key elements: the graphical element and the written element. The graphical element represents a vibrant mix of mobility services pointed directly at the individual user. The shape is dynamic and the colour range is exciting and energetic. It consists of an outer circle which depicts the wheel of a car and represents the vehicle automation aspect. Inside the circle several spokes (in blue) are placed which are connected with each other and with other smaller circles, representing the interconnectivity aspects of ICT4CART. These spokes meet the tyre of the wheel (in black), that in turn represents the infrastructure necessary for project implementation. The written element is in fact the project's short name and includes: the 'ICT' acronym in black and in blue the 'CART' acronym, standing for Connected and Automated Road Transport. For the number '4' (stands for "for") which connects the two main parts of the verbal element, the colour grey was selected as a more neutral one. The typography used is simple, direct and bold. It is an engaging device which runs throughout the designs that support the ICT4CART project.

The main colours for the project brand are those already used in the logo: the blue, grey and black colours. The blue is used as a variation and reminder of the blue that represents the European identity, prevalent in many EU funded projects.

The logo has been produced in several formats (including positive and negative formats) for different uses, and reproduction purposes (presentations, brochures, roll-up banners, website etc.) as outlined in the present guidelines.

1.1.1.3 Logo size and use

The master logo should always appear fully intact. The text should never be amended or removed. At the minimum size, always use the master logo in full. Each element and its position in relation to each other have been carefully designed and must never be stretched, altered or distorted. Master logos for all applications are available for use from the marketing department. Always follow these guidelines to ensure their consistent use.

When it is used with other graphic elements, it is advisable to leave free space within the two. Preferably, to each side of the logo, a minimum free space of '1/4 x' should be considered.

X is equivalent to the height of the icon of the logo.

Figure 5: ICT4CART logo - safe area

1.1.1.4 Logo variations

Figure 6: ICT4CART master logo

Figure 3: one colour logo

Figure 8: one colour reversed logo

Figure 9: social media-sized logo

Figure 2 - Master logo: full colours logo to be used on white background. This is the master version which should be mainly used.

Figure 3 – one colour logo: this version is to be used in the case in which the logo must be reproduced in black and white.

Figure 4 - one-colour reversed logo: to be used if the logo must appear on a dark coloured background.

Figure 5 – social media-sized logo: to be used as a “profile picture” for social media accounts (i.e. Twitter).

1.1.1.5 Social media visuals: Twitter banners

To support ICT4CART social media promotion, a set of banners has been created for the dedicated-ICT4CART Twitter account. More social media banners will be created, subject to the project needs.

Banner 1 (figure 6) is the main cover of the Twitter account; banner 2 (figure 7), 3 (figure 8) and 4 (figure 9) have been made available to partners, in order to provide visual support for the content they envisage to post and share through their corporate and personal media accounts.

The use of ICT4CART banners will ensure the project’s consistency and create a recognizable visual identity for online activities for the content which will be disseminated through various channels and tools.

Figure 10: ICT4CART Twitter cover banner

Figure 11: ICT4CART Twitter post banner 1

Figure 12: ICT4CART Twitter post banner 2

Figure 13: ICT4CART Twitter post banner 3

1.1.1.6 Colour palette

Colour is a powerful mean of identification. Consistent use of ICT4CART logo colours will increase project's visibility, uniformity and integrity and the awareness and recognition for its brand.

The coloured logo is made up of a range of colours: it is required to use the full colour logo on a white background, as depicted in figure 10 below.

Black	Cyan	Colour grey	Colour grey 70%
C = 0 M = 0 Y = 0 K = 100	C = 70 M = 0 Y = 3 K = 0	C = 47 M = 42 Y = 39 K = 25	C = 33 M = 29 Y = 27 K = 18
R = 0 G = 0 B = 0	R = 23 G = 185 B = 236	R = 116 G = 113 B = 115	R = 158 G = 157 B = 155
#000000	#17B9EC	#747173	#9E9B9D

Figure 14: ICT4CART colours

Colour is a primary mean of visual communication. The use of a limited colour palette will assist the ICT4CART project in building a strong external recognition.

Core colours of ICT4CART are a vibrant blue, black and grey, used within the master logo. They can be used carefully as highlight or background colours in documents. As mentioned above, the blue is a variation of the colour that is used to represent the European identity, given the project has been supported/funded by the EU. Grey and black are considered as identifiable colours, with elements related to mobility, road, infrastructure, aluminium and iron.

1.1.1.7 Logo and colour palette incorrect use

The following section includes a few examples of incorrect use of ICT4CART logo and colour palette. The below-reported cases (figure 11) will help you to avoid inconsistencies and ensure the proper utilisation of ICT4CART communication tools and visuals.

Figure 15: ICT4CART examples of incorrect use

1.1.1.8 ICT4CART Tagline

ICT4CART brand identity includes a tagline which is reported on the social media banners and will also be included in the homepage of the ICT4CART website. The tagline, “A connected future for automated driving” summarises the main aim and core idea of the project and should be used, along with visuals and graphic elements, to reinforce the message and build a stronger online identity.

It is advisable to use it together with the project logo, when possible, or as the basic opening/closing/accompanying message when producing press releases, presentations or printed material such as brochures, leaflets etc.

1.1.1.9 ICT4CART Brand typography

The primary identity typeface is **Panton**, and it should be used in all printed and online materials. It is highly suggested to use **12 of the 54 styles** available. The right choice must be made according to the specific material and criteria of the designer.

As a basic rule, the use of **Panton Extrabold** (figure 12) is required in the main heading.

For subheadings, it is compulsory to use **Panton Bold**, and for body copy, the **Panton Regular** (figure 13-14).

Figure 16: Panton Bold and Extrabold for headings and subheadings

Panton
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890,./=+&_€@![%]\$|?>":

Figure 17 Panton Regular for body text

Thin
 Thin Italic
 Light
 Light Italic
 Regular
 Regular Italic
Bold
Bold Italic
Extrabold
Extrabold Italic
Black
Black Italic

Figure 18: Panton - all variations

For MS Office, the use **Tahoma** fonts is required.

Tahoma

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890,./=+&_£@!(%)\$|?>”:

Tahoma Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890,./=+&_£@!(%)\$|?>”:

1.1.2 MS Office templates

1.1.2.1 PowerPoint Presentation

A PowerPoint (PPT) presentation template of the project has been developed. All partners have been instructed to make use of the available template when presenting the project internally, as well as externally to third parties.

Project partners can add their logo to the master PPT; a placeholder has been incorporated on the PPT cover, on the left side of ICT4CART logo (the placeholder is visible in Slide Master view).

The partners' logo should be included in a one-colour version, to align with the blue background of this slide, or in a white box (this option, though, it is not preferable, as it would interfere with the project identity and design). In case more logos need to be added, the best option would be to include them on the very last slide and not on the cover presentation slide.

Partners are suggested to check with ERTICO the final layout before presenting.

Furthermore, partners should inform the ICT4CART Project Coordinator and the project Steering Committee where and when presentations are given. Detailed description of the dissemination procedures, related to presentations, is available through the common online collaborative tool (Redmine). The template is available in the corresponding folder on the Redmine depository platform. Indicative screenshots of the PPT template are available in Annex 1 of the present document (figures 15-18).

1.1.2.2 Word template

An official Word template has been also developed. All partners have been instructed to use this template in order to produce internal reports and official project deliverables.

The template has been developed according to ICT4CART brand identity, including the project logo, fonts and colours. The template is also compliant with the EC requirements regarding the official project deliverables. ICT4CART template is available in the corresponding folder on the Redmine repository platform. Indicative screenshots of the PPT template are available in Annex 1 of the present document (figures 19 - 21).

1.1.3 Notices/Disclaimer

ICT4CART project is co-funded by the European Union. Any dissemination, communication and publication materials (in any form, including electronic) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results, must clearly acknowledge the receipt of EU funding (unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible) through:

- The display of the EU emblem and
- The acknowledgement of EU funding by including the following text:

For Communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 768953”.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

“This [infrastructure][equipment] [insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 768953”.

According to EC instructions, all project communication material must acknowledge the EU funding by including the appropriate EC disclaimer as stipulated in the article 38 of ICT4CART Grand Agreement and by displaying the correct EU emblem, with an appropriate prominence.

A complementary disclaimer will also be included in the production of any dissemination/communication material (as indicated in the article 38.1.3 of ICT4CART GA, related to exclusion of Agency’s responsibility) stating:

“The content of this material reflects only the authors’ view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

1.1.4 Annexes

1.1.4.1 Annex 1: Power Point template

Figure 19: PPT Cover

Figure 20: Section header

Figure 21: Regular text slide

Figure 22: Closing slide

1.1.4.2 *Annex 1: Word template*

Figure 23: Word template - Cover page

Project logo

Document Control Sheet

Deliverable number:	
Deliverable responsible:	
Workpackage:	
Editor:	

Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail

Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
V0.1			

Abstract
This document presents xxx

Legal Disclaimer

The document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Figure 24: Word template - Document control sheet

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

Explain why the document is created, what purpose it serves in the project, who are the "customers" e.g. what WPs or Tasks are going to use the deliverable – what question it answers

Text

1.2 Targeted audience

Explained who is the intended audience for the deliverables, e.g. the clients of this deliverables, if public, who is likely to be interested in the content: research, policy, business

Text

2 Chapter 1

2.1 Sub-heading 1

The first chapter is expected to explain the content and the structure of the document, what will be in the next chapters

Text

2.2 Sub-heading 2

Text ... as shown in **Table 1** below ..

Table 1–Title 1

2.3 Sub-heading 3

3 Chapter 2

Figure 25: Word template - content pages

Annex 2 – ICT4CART template of press release circulated after the kick off meeting

ICT4CART: A connected future for Automated Driving

(Name of the organization) is delighted to announce its participation in the eagerly awaited ICT4CART project, officially launched in Athens, Greece in September 2018. ICT4CART, is an EU-funded H2020 innovation action and consists of 21 partners from 9 EU countries, united in their vision to build a sustainable future for connected and automated vehicles.

The aim of ICT4CART, coordinated by the Institute of Communication & Computer Systems (ICCS), is to provide the ICT infrastructure to enable the transition towards road transport automation. ICT4CART is bringing together, adapting and improving technological advances from different industries, mainly the telecommunication, automotive and IT industries. The project adopts a hybrid communication approach where all the major wireless technologies, i.e. cellular, ITS G5 and LTE-V, are integrated under flexible “sliced” network architecture. This architecture will ensure performance and resilience for different groups of applications according to the needs of higher levels of automation. On top of that, a distributed IT environment for data aggregation and analytics will be implemented.

Quote from partner and comment on role.

The result of this allows seamless integration and the exchange of data and services between all the different actors, encouraging third parties to develop, deliver and provide innovative services, thus creating new business opportunities. Cyber-security and data privacy aspects will be considered throughout the entire ICT infrastructure. In addition, innovative accurate localisation services, exploiting the cellular network and information from other sources, such as on-board sensors, especially in complex areas (e.g. urban), will be addressed. Standardisation and interoperability are of high interest within ICT4CART in order to ensure the project facilitates the transition to higher levels of automation. In this context, issues related to the frequency spectrum will be investigated, and with the organisation of relevant workshops the engagement of policy makers and public authorities will be ensured.

To achieve its objectives ICT4CART, instead of working in generic solutions with questionable impact, it builds on four specific high-value use cases (urban and highway) which will be demonstrated and validated under real-life conditions at the project test sites in Austria, Germany, Italy and across the Italian-Austrian border.

For more information, please contact (insert name of contact person).

Annex 3 – Repository scientific journals and European and international events

No.	Title of journal/magazine	Website	Description
Intelligent Transportation Systems			
1	IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems journal	https://www.ieee-itss.org/its-transactions	<p>T-ITS is published quarterly, in March, June, September, and December. All issues of ITS Transactions are digitally archived in IEEE Xplore.</p> <p>Scope: Improved planning, design, management, and the control of future transportation systems requires conducting both basic and applied research to expand the knowledge base on transportation. The Transactions serve as a forum for the technological aspects of information technology to transportation, and focuses on the design, analysis, and control of information technology as it is applied to transportation systems.</p>
2	IET Intelligent Transport Systems Journal	http://digital-library.theiet.org/content/journals/iet-its	<p>IET Intelligent Transport Systems is an interdisciplinary journal devoted to research into the practical applications of ITS and infrastructures. The scope of the journal includes the following:</p> <p>Sustainable traffic solutions; deployments with enabling technologies; pervasive monitoring ; applications; demonstrations and evaluation; economic and behavioural analyses of ITS services and scenario; data Integration and analytics; information collection and processing; image processing applications in ITS; ITS aspects of electric vehicles; autonomous vehicles; connected vehicle systems; in-vehicle ITS, safety and vulnerable road user aspects; mobility as a service systems; traffic management and control; public transport systems technologies; fleet and public transport logistics; emergency and incident management; demand management and electronic payment systems; traffic related air pollution management; policy and institutional issues; interoperability, standards and architectures; funding scenarios; enforcement; human machine interaction; education, training and outreach.</p>
3	Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems: Technology, Planning, and Operations	https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/gits20/current	<p>The Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems is devoted to scholarly research on the development, planning, management, operation and evaluation of intelligent transportation systems.</p> <p>The Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems is especially interested in research that leads to improved planning and operation of the transportation system through the application of new technologies. The journal is particularly interested in research that adds to the scientific understanding of the impacts that intelligent transportation systems can have on accessibility, congestion, pollution, safety, security, noise, and energy and resource consumption.</p>
4	International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research	https://link.springer.com/journal/13177 , http://www.its-jp.org/english/ijit/	<p>The International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research provides a global forum for the discussion of effective solutions for ITS, to meet the needs of the world. It is the only international platform to foster wide-ranging</p>

			<p>discussion across disciplines by bringing together a broad-based audience for solutions-oriented information and discussion.</p> <p>The journal serves a multi-disciplinary set of researchers and specialists in fields ranging from transportation, electrical, mechanical, and traffic engineering, as well as in policy planning, economics, and psychology. It reaches across disciplines to find solutions to the difficult issues surrounding the future transportation system and its impact on society.</p> <p>Area covered: Sensor Technology, Communication Technology and ITS Applications, Vehicle Control and Automated Driving, Safety Improvement and Human Interface, Traffic Control, Traffic Planning, Urban Engineering, Transportation Policy, Traffic Economy, Environmental Sustainability, Traffic Psychology, Other Applied Technologies.</p>
5	Journal of Advanced Transportation	https://www.hindawi.com/journals/jat/	<p>The Journal of Advanced Transportation (JAT) is a fully peer reviewed international journal in transportation research areas related to public transit, road traffic, transport networks and air transport.</p> <p>It publishes theoretical and innovative papers on analysis, design, operations, optimization and planning of multi-modal transport networks, transit & traffic systems, transport technology and traffic safety. Urban rail and bus systems, Pedestrian studies, traffic flow theory and control, Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) and automated and/or connected vehicles are some topics of interest.</p> <p>Highway engineering, railway engineering and logistics do not fall within the aims and scope of JAT.</p>
Communication, Cyber-security, Computing and IoT Technologies			
6	IEEE Communications Magazine	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/aboutJournal.jsp?punumber=35	<p>IEEE Communications Magazine, considered by most to be their most important member benefit, provides timely information on all aspects of communications: monthly feature articles describe technology, systems, services, market trends, development methods, regulatory and policy issues, and significant global events. These articles are complemented by a variety of departments, including: Conference Calendar, Book Reviews, the Global Communications Newsletter, Scanning the Literature, New products and Product Spotlights, Society News, Your Internet Connection, News from JSAC, and the CommuniCrostic puzzle. Articles are tutorial in nature and written in a style comprehensible to readers outside the specialty of the article. Mathematical equations are generally not used (in justified cases up to three simple equations may be allowed with the consent of the Guest Editor.</p>
7	IEEE Transaction on Mobile Computing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/aboutJournal.jsp?punumber=7755	<p>IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing focuses on the key technical issues related to (a) architectures, (b) support services, (c) algorithm/protocol design and analysis, (d) mobile environments, (e) mobile communication systems, (f) applications, and (g) emerging technologies. Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following: a) Architectures - Mobile networks and hosts, Agents and proxies, Mobility management, mobile agent and proxy architectures Integrated</p>

			<p>wireline and wireless systems, Planning and standardization. b) Support Services - Mobility and roaming, Nomadic computing, Multimedia Operating system support, Power management. c) Algorithm/Protocol Design and Analysis - Online and mobile environments, Limited bandwidth, Intermittent connectivity. d) Mobile Environments - Data and knowledge management, Performance modeling and characterization, Security, scalability and reliability, Design, management and operation, Systems and technologies. e) Mobile Communication Systems - Wireless, cellular and spread-spectrum systems, Multi-user and multi-access techniques and algorithms, Multi-channel processing, Channel coding, Data coding and compression. f) Applications - Location-dependent and sensitive, Nomadic computing, Wearable computers and body area networks, Multimedia applications and multimedia signal processing, Pervasive computing, Wireless sensor networks. g) Emerging Technologies.</p>
8	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=7693	<p>The IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications publishes high-quality manuscripts on advances in the state-of-the-art of wireless communications. Both theoretical contributions (including new techniques, concepts, and analyses) and practical contributions (including system experiments and prototypes, and new applications) are encouraged. The general scope of the Transactions includes, but is not limited to, the following: Modulation and coding , Detection and estimation, Diversity techniques and equalization, Propagation and channel characterization, Fading countermeasures, Multiuser detection, Signal separation and interference rejection, DSP applications to wireless systems, Broadband wireless communications, Network architectures and protocols, with an emphasis on physical and link layer communication, Adaptive antennas for wireless systems, Multiple access techniques, Space-time processing , Synchronization techniques, Software radio, Resource allocation and interference management, Multirate and multicarrier communications, Security, privacy, and authentication, Experimental and prototype results, Systems and services including mobile satellites, wireless local loops, wireless LANs, wireless PBX, and PCS/cellular.</p> <p>In addition, papers on specific topics or on more non-traditional topics related to specific application areas, are encouraged. Examples include Simulation tools and methodologies for design, analysis, rapid prototyping, performance prediction, and cellular system engineering; Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing; MIMO systems, and Wireless over optical.</p>
9	IET Communications	http://digital-library.theiet.org/content/journals/iet-com	<p>IET Communications covers the fundamental and generic research for a better understanding of communication technologies to harness the signals for better performing communication systems using various wired and/or wireless media. This journal is particularly interested in research papers reporting novel solutions to the dominating problems of noise, interference, timing and errors for reduction systems</p>

			deficiencies such as wasting scarce resources such as spectra, energy and bandwidth.
10	IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/aboutJournal.jsp?punumber=9424	<p>Knowledge in the IST (Information Society Technologies) field envisions a technology bifurcation in the field of intelligent automation systems and real-time middle-ware technologies in the next 5-10 years. This technology bifurcation extends networked embedded intelligence at the real-time production control and re-scheduling levels further than is currently possible, allowing for a completely new range of intelligent automation products and services. Such products and services enables new paradigms of production and new concepts of product-services and new intelligent production automation concepts, which are more agile, flexible and integrated, based on agent-based technology. The scope of the journal considers the industry's transition towards more knowledge-based production and systems organization and considers production from a more holistic perspective, encompassing not only hardware and software, but also people and the way in which they learn and share knowledge. Such a framework accommodates ideas related to: radical shifts in industrial structures with capabilities in networks and mastering; new hybrid technologies; development of new processes and devices and flexible and intelligent manufacturing systems; tools for the control of complex distributed production systems; realization of an ambient intelligence landscape at industrial level. The journal focuses on the following main topics: Flexible, collaborative factory automation, Distributed industrial control and computing paradigms, Internet-based monitoring and control systems, Real-time control software for industrial processes, Java and Jini in industrial environments, Control of wireless sensors and actuators, Systems interoperability and human machine interface.</p>
11	Elsevier Journal of Network and Computer Applications	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-network-and-computer-applications	<p>The Journal of Network and Computer Applications welcomes research contributions, surveys and notes in all areas relating to computer networks and applications thereof. The following list of sample-topics is by no means to be understood as restricting contributions to the topics mentioned:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • new design techniques, interesting or novel applications, components or standards • computer networks with tools such as WWW • emerging standards for internet protocols <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wireless networks • Mobile Computing • emerging computing models such as cloud computing, grid computing • emerging network protocols such as sensor networks, delay tolerant networks, Internet of things • applications of networked systems for remote collaboration and telemedicine • applications of an educational, transactional and cooperational nature

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • applications of security in computer and networks
12	IEEE Transactions on Big Data	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/aboutJournal.jsp?punumber=6687317	<p>The IEEE Transactions on Big Data publishes peer reviewed articles with big data as the main focus. The articles will provide cross disciplinary innovative research ideas and applications results for big data including novel theory, algorithms and applications. Research areas for big data include, but are not restricted to, big data analytics, big data visualization, big data curation and management, big data semantics, big data infrastructure, big data standards, big data performance analyses, intelligence from big data, scientific discovery from big data security, privacy, and legal issues specific to big data. Applications of big data in the fields of endeavor where massive data is generated are of particular interest.</p>
Automation			
13	International Journal of Automation and Control	http://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijsac	<p>IJAAC addresses the evolution and realisation of the theory, algorithms, techniques, schemes and tools for any kind of automation and control platforms including macro, micro and nano scale machineries and systems, with emphasis on implications that state-of-the-art technology choices have on both the feasibility and practicability of the intended applications. This perspective acknowledges the complexity of the automation, instrumentation and process control methods and delineates itself as an interface between the theory and practice existing in parallel over diverse spheres.</p>
14	IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/aboutJournal.jsp?punumber=8856	<p>The IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering (T-ASE) publishes fundamental papers on Automation, emphasizing scientific results that advance efficiency, quality, productivity, and reliability. T-ASE encourages interdisciplinary approaches from computer science, control systems, electrical engineering, mathematics, mechanical engineering, operations research, and other fields. T-ASE welcomes results relevant to industries such as agriculture, biotechnology, healthcare, home automation, maintenance, manufacturing, pharmaceuticals, retail, security, service, supply chains, and transportation. T-ASE addresses a research community willing to integrate knowledge across disciplines and industries. For this purpose, each paper includes a Note to Practitioners that summarizes how its results can be applied or how they might be extended to apply in practice.</p>
15	International Journal of Vehicle Autonomous Systems	https://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijvas	<p>IJVAS is an established international authoritative reference in the field of vehicle autonomous systems research and development. Such systems aim to increase accident avoidance and road capacity, improve the travel experience by relieving occupants of driving/navigation chores, reduce total vehicle numbers and eliminate some of the services/infrastructure associated with motoring today</p>

Table 13: List of ICT4CART proposed scientific Journals

Date	Event	Location	Website	Important deadlines
13-17/01/2019	Transportation Research Board (TRB)	Washington, D.C	http://www.trb.org/AnnualMeeting/AnnualMeeting.aspx	
14-17/01/2019	ICDCN 2019 : International Conference on Distributed Computing and Networking	Bangalore, India	https://events.csa.iisc.ac.in/icdcn2019/	<i>Important Dates:</i> Abstract Registration Due Jul 15, 2018 Submission Deadline Jul 22, 2018 Notification Due Sep 20, 2019 Final Version Due Oct 26, 2019
25-28/2/2019	MWC19	Barcelona, Spain	https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/	
11-15/03/2019	SPT-IoT 2019 : The Third International Workshop on Security, Privacy and Trust in the Internet of Things	Kyoto, Japan	https://sites.google.com/view/spt-iot/home	<i>Important Dates:</i> Submission Deadline Nov 10, 2018 Notification Due Dec 22, 2018 Final Version Due Jan 11, 2019
21-22/3/2019	3rd International Conference on Recent Advances in Signal Processing, Telecommunications & Computing (SigTelCom)	HaNoi, Vietnam	http://www.sigtel.com.net/2019/	
28/4-1/5/2019	2019 IEEE 89th Vehicular Technology Conference	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	http://www.ieeevtc.org/vtc2019spring/	<i>Important Dates</i> Submit papers for review: 15 October 2018 Submit tutorial proposals for review: 15 October 2018 (Extended) Submit workshop papers for review: 22 January 2019 Regular paper acceptance: 8 January 2019 Workshop paper acceptance: 16 February 2019 All final papers due: 28 February 2019
2-4/05/2019	IoT BDS 2019: International Conference on Internet of Things, Big Data and Security	Heraklion, Crete, Greece	http://iotbds.org/Home.aspx	<i>Important Dates:</i> Regular Paper Submission: December 10, 2018 Regular Paper Authors Notification: February 7, 2019 Regular Paper Camera Ready and Registration: February 21, 2019

Date	Event	Location	Website	Important deadlines
20-24/5/2019	IEEE International Conference on Communications	Shanghai , China	http://icc2019.ieee-icc.org/	<i>IMPORTANT DATES</i> Paper Submission: 14 October 2018 Acceptance Notification: 27 January 2019 Camera-Ready: 24 February 2019
20-24/5/2019	IEEE Robotics and Automation Society, ICRA	Montreal , Canada	https://www.icra2019.org/	
21-23/5/2019	Autonomus Vehicle Software Symposium	Munich	https://autonomusvehicle-software.com/en/	
30-4/6/2019	Eighth International Conference on Advances in Vehicular Systems, Technologies and Applications	Rome	https://www.iaria.org/conferences/VEHICULAR.html	
3-6/6/2019	ITS European Congress	Netherlands	https://2019.itsineurope.com/about/	
4-6/6/2019	TU-Automotive	Detroit	https://automotive.knect365.com/tu-auto-detroit/	
9-12/6/2019	2019 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)	Paris	https://www.acofnf.org/conf_161415.html	
18-21/6/2019	EuCNC 2019- European Conference on Networks and Communications	Valencia, Spain	https://www.eucnc.eu/announcement-eucnc-2019/	
24-28/6/2019	International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing Conference	Tangier, Marocco	http://iwcmc.org/2019/	<i>Important Dates:</i> Paper Submission Deadline: Jan. 10, 2019 Paper Acceptance Notification: March 30, 2019 Camera-ready Submissions: April 30, 2019 Registration for Authors: April 30, 2019
7-10/7/2019	ICDCS 2019 : International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems	Texas, USA	http://theory.utdallas.edu/ICDCS2019/	<i>Importsnt Dates:</i> Abstract Registration Due Jan 5, 2019 Submission Deadline Jan 12, 2019 Notification Due Mar 28, 2019 Final Version Due Apr 3, 2019
15-18/7/2019	AUVSI- Autonomous Vehicles Symposium	Orlando, Florida	https://www.auvsi.org/autonomous-vehicles-symposium-moves-orlando-2019	

Date	Event	Location	Website	Important deadlines
15-16/09/2019	ICE2019 – 14th International Conference on Engines & Vehicles	Naples, USA	http://www.paregen.eu/events/1123/	
21-25/10/2019	26th ITS world congress	Singapore	https://itsworldcongress2019.com/	https://itsworldcongress2019.com/programme/paper-submission/
27-30/10/2019	ITSC 2019 : IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference	New Zealand	https://www.itsc2019.org/	
4-8/11/2019	2019 IEEE ICCVE- International Conference on Connected Vehicles and Expo	Graz- Austria	https://www.iccve2019.com/	
26-30/4/2020	TRA	Helsinki, Finland	https://www.traconference.eu/presenting-host-tra2020-helsinki-finland/	

Table 14 List of ICT4CART related European & International events